

PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF USING NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

Khusanova Nazokat Sharipjonovna

Teacher of school number 10 in Rishtan, Fergana

Annotation: In the article given some opinions about practical significance of using new pedagogical technologies in the educational process.

Key words: teaching, learner, teacher, technology, education, process.

The method of using interactive methods and pedagogical technologies in the educational process, the number of innovative technologies and interactive methods has increased a lot. We present the methodology of using some pedagogical technologies and interactive methods that are widespread in educational institutions and can be used in specific subjects and subjects.

Technology “Step by step”

The purpose of technology. To help students to think freely, independently and logically, to work as a team, to search, to gather ideas and form a theoretical and practical understanding from them, to be able to influence the team with their opinion, to approve it, as well as to explain the basic concepts of the topic. teaching to apply the knowledge acquired in giving.

Technology “Water-wheel”

The purpose of technology. Teaching students to think logically during the lesson, to express their thoughts independently, to evaluate themselves, to work individually and in groups, to respect the opinions of others, to choose the right one from many opinions.

Technology “Boomerang”

The purpose of technology. In the course of the educational process, students' learning of handouts individually and in groups, as well as monitoring and evaluating the extent to which the texts in the handouts are mastered through

conversation - discussion and various questions. Making it possible for each student to get his own grades during the educational process.

From work experience of teachers

Teachers using this technology have organized the teaching and training process using the following texts based on the subject of their study subjects or a free topic. For example,

1. Topic: "Flowers and their history, importance in life.

Handouts:

To group 1 - Since when are flowers grown?

To group 2 - The importance of flowers in some peoples.

To group 3 - About the symbolic meaning of roses?

To group 4 - What does the lily flower mean to the Egyptians?

2. Topic: "Oriental etiquette"

Handouts:

To the 1st group - Statement of respect for teachers

To the 2nd group - Kindred - the manners of dealing between clans

To the 3rd group - Quni - manners of behavior between neighbors

To group 4 - Etiquette between friends

Technology "Communication"

The purpose of technology. Based on the selected topic and problem, to determine the opinions of students and their relationship to this topic, to help them independently come to a common opinion and draw correct conclusions, to create conditions for them to argue freely, to engage in communication and teach them to be able to communicate.

Technology "Dispute"

In order for students to improve their interaction in educational groups, to quickly get used to each other or to have good relations with each other, it is

advisable to organize debates between them sometimes. . Because such debates greatly help students to clarify their thoughts, to clarify their relationship to life and various problems. Students can choose and propose topics for discussion.

We highlight some topics for discussion below:

- Who can be said to be the perfect person of our time?
- Who can be called a cultured person?
- How are you living?
- Is your life interesting?
- What should a true friend be like?
- My character is like this...
- Where does carelessness come from?
- Fashion and me
- What is the price of a free item?
- What is merit, what is sin?

Effective discussion depends on pre-prepared questions to discuss the chosen topic.

Here are some approximate questions for debates on some topics:

Topic: Who can be called a cultured person?

Questions:

- What is culture?
- What is moral culture?
- What does human culture consist of?
- Which of the following qualities of a cultured person would you put first (politeness, resourcefulness, knowledge, eloquence)?
- Can all educated people be called cultured?
- Is it possible to determine whether people are cultured by the way they speak and speak?
- What should you do to be cultured?
- Who can be called cultured?

- Do you consider yourself cultured?
- What is the role of ethics in terms of personality?
- How to be cultured?

With the help of such methods, students' independent thinking grows, their outlook expands, and a feeling of not being ashamed to express their opinion is formed. These have a positive effect on the effectiveness of education.

REFERENCES

1. Shokhistakhon N. Use of " Learning a Foreign Language at Stations" in Foreign Language Classes //International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 109-111.
2. Xamidovna N. S. On The Influence of The Phonetic Laws of The Uzbek Language in The Teaching of German //Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices. – 2021. – Т. 3. – С. 46-48.
3. Khamidovna N. S. On The Use of Infinitive Groups in German and Uzbek Languages //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 202-204.
4. Xasanova O. Pedagogical Importance of Mnemotechnics in Increasing The Vocabulary Of Uzbek Language Learners in German Language //Science and Education. – 2021. – Т. 1. – С. 1-6.
5. Makhmudovna A. S. et al. THE CONTENT OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES //World Bulletin of Social Sciences. – 2021. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 39-40.
6. Xasanova O. USING MNEMOTECHNICS IN TEACHING GERMAN ARTICLES FOR UZBEK STUDENTS //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2019. – Т. 7. – №. 12.
7. Хасанова О. К. К. ВИДЫ МНЕМОНИКИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ НЕМЕЦКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ //Вопросы науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 40 (124).
8. Vokhidovna K. K. Teaching Foreign Languages at Preschools //International Journal on Integrated Education. – Т. 4. – №. 3. – С. 237-239.

9. Badirovna S. N. METHODS OF TEACHING GERMAN //Thematics Journal of English Language Teaching. – 2022. – T. 6. – №. 1.